

Semiconductor nanoparticles (CdS, ZnS and $Zn_xCd_{1-x}S$) in reverse micellar media[†]

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Manuscript received 31 December 2002

Nanoparticles CdS, ZnS and mixed crystals of $Zn_xCd_{1-x}S$ can be generated *in situ* in AOT-heptane-water and CTAB-chloroform-water microemulsions using an ultrasonic processor. The nanoparticles exhibit the "quantum size effect". The average diameter of nanoparticles, as manifested in the photoabsorption threshold of colloidal semiconductors, increases as the water content of reverse micelles and the concentration of ϕ -state particles increases. The composition of mixed sulfides and water content (pool size) of inverted micelles can be varied systematically and the band gap energies of the semiconductor particles can be determined from photoabsorption threshold (edges). A method is proposed for determining the bulk optical dielectric constants of solid solutions of two semiconductor employing the Brus equations.

In recent years, considerable attention has been devoted to the studies on 'nanoparticles', clusters of atoms or molecules of metals or semiconductors, ranging in sizes 1-10 nm. Nanoparticles of semiconductors are not thermodynamically stable and require some sort of kinetic stabilization. Organized surfactant assemblies such as vesicles or reverse micelles may be used as the incorporation media of these particles¹⁻⁴. The reverse micelles are optically transparent and favour the synthesis of more monodispersed nano crystallites^{4,5}. There is an increasing realization that solutes present in the waterpools of reversed micelles exchange freely with other water pools through intermicellar collisions. Most of those have come from rapid mixing or stopped flow kinetic studies of various reactions in reversed micelles. The possibility of such an exchange was first pointed out by Menger *et al.*⁶ when they observed hydrolysis of an ester to occur on mixing of two AOT-octane-water solutions, one containing the ester and the other imidazole. In similar experiments, Eicke *et al.*^{7,8} observed the enhanced fluorescence on complexation of Tb^{3+} with hydroxy-phenylacetic acid (HPA) as a probe. Exchange of solute was monitored during of mixing of two AOT-isooctane-water solutions, one containing water-solubilized Tb^{3+} ions and the other water-solubilized HPA. The enhanced fluorescence was observed as rapidly as the mixing of two solutions. A transient dimer model for the coalescing water droplets was proposed with the opening of a water channel at the point of collision. The exchange of solutes has been pictured to take place through diffusion through these channels during the collision time ($10^{-10} - 10^{-11}$ s).

From various physicochemical measurements like viscosity, dielectric studies, light scattering, small angle neutron and X-ray scattering measurements, it has been shown that the radius of reverse micelles is linearly dependent on W ($W = [H_2O]/[surfactant]$) and so the particle size may be controlled by varying the value of W . The average particle diameter also depends on the relative amounts of cation and anion from which the semiconductors are formed ($x = [M^{2+}]/[X^{Y-}]$)⁹. So far as the nature of the water in the pool is concerned the water acquires bulk character as the size of the pool increases, i.e. as W becomes large (say around 50).

Nanosized semiconductor particles with diameter ranging between 1 and 10 nm possess properties which lie in the region of transition between the molecular level and the bulk-phase. The size-dependent development of bulk electronic properties (quantum size effect) in nanocrystals of semiconductors can be understood in terms of an expression proposed by Brus,¹⁰

$$E(R) = E_g + \frac{\hbar^2}{8R^2} (m_e^{-1} + m_h^{-1}) - \frac{1.8 e^2}{\epsilon R} \quad (1)$$

where, E_g represents the bulk band gap energy, $E(R)$ the band gap energy of the semiconductor particles having radius R , m_e and m_h denote the effective masses of the electron and hole and ϵ designates the bulk optical dielectric constant of the semiconductor. It is evident from eq. (1) that ϵ of a semiconductor can be determined from the intercept of the straight-line obtained by plotting $R\Delta E_g$ against $1/R$ where ΔE_g is the difference between $E(R)$ and E_g .

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

In general, the quantum-size effect shows large shifts in fundamental absorption edge and this in turn leads to enhanced redox potentials for photoexcited electrons and holes in semiconductor nanoparticles. These nanoparticles are expected to show extremely interesting photochemistry due to quantum confinement of the electron/hole pair upon excitation. In most of the cases intense recombination emission which is red-shifted from the absorption threshold is observed^{11,12}. The red-shift of emission is ascribed to local traps arising from surface defects.

Absorption spectra :

Absorption spectra of pure semiconductors CdS and ZnS have been presented in Figs. 1-3 and Figs.4-6, respectively, in AOT-heptane water reverse micelles at various *W* values.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of CdS in 0.058 mol dm⁻³ AOT in heptane at various *W* values.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of CdS in 0.058 mol dm⁻³ AOT in heptane at various concentrations of CdS prepared in *W* = 5 reverse micelles.

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra of CdS in 0.232 mol dm⁻³ AOT in heptane at various concentration of CdS prepared in *W* = 5 reverse micelles.

Fig. 4. Absorption spectra of ZnS in 0.058 mol dm⁻³ AOT in heptane at various *W* values.

Fig. 5. Absorption spectra of ZnS in 0.058 mol dm⁻³ AOT in heptane at various concentration of ZnS prepared in *W* = 5 reverse micelles.

Figs. 7 and 8 represent absorption spectra for mixed semiconductor Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanoparticles in AOT-heptane-water and CTAB-chloroform-water reverse micelles, in each case at a given *W* with varying *x* values. As a result of variation of *W* and hence of particle size, the so-called

quantum size effect causes a perturbation in electronic structure of the semiconductor nanoparticles¹³. This gives a widening of the forbidden band and as seen from Table 1 that a blue-shift of the absorption band edge occurs with decrease in size of the water pool. The average radius of the

Fig. 6. Absorption spectra of ZnS in $0.232 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ AOT in heptane at various concentration of ZnS prepared in $W = 5$ reverse micelles

Fig. 7. Absorption spectra of $Zn_x Cd_{1-x}S$ stabilised in AOT-heptane-water $W = 5$ and $x = 0, 0.14, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 0.86$ and 1 for a, b, c, d, e, f and g respectively

Fig. 8. Absorption spectra of $Zn_x Cd_{1-x}S$ stabilised in CTAB-chloroform-water $W = 3.5$ and $x = 0, 0.14, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 0.86$ and 1 for a, b, c, d, e, f and g respectively

Table 1. Absorption thresholds (λ_{abs}) of CdS and ZnS in AOT reverse micelles

W	[AOT] mol dm^{-3}	[Semiconductor] $\times 10^4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	λ_{abs} for CdS nm	λ_{abs} for ZnS nm
4	0.058	5	423	302
	0.232	2	–	316
5	0.058	5	420	302
	0.232	4	450	318
5	0.058	6	430	305
	0.232	6	465	322
5	0.058	8	435	308
	0.232	8	476	329
5	0.058	1	440	310
	0.232	1	480	333
6	0.058	1	427	305
8	0.058	5	430	310
10	0.058	5	433	312
12	0.058	5	440	320

particles can be related to the absorption threshold. Because of discrete energy levels in quantised nanoparticles of very uniform size (monodispersia), one can expect to have a well defined structure in the absorption edge. The absorption edge of CdS and ZnS shows a long tail at higher values of W (Figs. 1 and 4). For mixed semiconductor $Zn_x Cd_{1-x}S$ nanoparticles, Figs. 7 and 8 also show such long tails particularly at higher zinc concentration indicating a broad distribution of particle sizes (polydispersion). The results presented in Table 1 also reveal that for $W=5$, the average particle radius of CdS and ZnS increases as concentration of dispersed particles increases at a fixed concentration of AOT. Petit *et al*⁹ reported similar observation for CdS formed by bubbling H_2S through mixed micelles of cadmium and sodium AOT. The particle size also increases with increasing water content, i.e. W as is evident from Figs. 1, 4 and 7 for CdS, ZnS and $Zn_x Cd_{1-x}S$ respectively.

The results depicted in Table 1 also indicate that for a given value of W , the photoabsorption threshold of CdS and ZnS nanoparticles get red-shifted as [AOT] is increased from 0.058 to 0.232 M. This implies that the radius of the spherical water pool is related to surfactant concentration, W being maintained constant at 5. Similar conclusion has been drawn by Atik and Thomas¹⁴ in interpreting the luminescence quenching of $[Ru(bpy)_3]^{2+}$ by $[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}$ in AOT reverse micelle.

Size-effect on physical properties of atoms/molecules has been reported by different workers in recent years. Moulik *et al.*^{15a} studied the absorption spectra of nano-copper-ferrocyanide particles in AOT/H₂O heptane reverse micelle and Arcolo *et al.*^{15b} that of copper-AOT complex in AOT/H₂O/CCl₄ reverse micelle. In both the cases blue-shift was observed with increasing *W*. Pal *et al.*¹⁶ prepared nano metal particles of Cu, Ag, and Pd of various sizes and reported an increase in reducing power of the particles.

Fluorescence :

Nanoparticles of CdS stabilised in AOT-heptane-water reverse micelles exhibit a broad fluorescence band with a broad peak at a wavelength longer than the edge of absorption. This is illustrated in Figs. 9–11. The band may be ascribed to the removal of electrons/holes through recombination by surface charges. The energy of these traps is related to the size of the particles¹⁷. It is evident from Fig. 9 and Table 5 that the fluorescence maximum is shifted to longer wavelength with the increase in pool-size of reverse micelles and this can be explained by the increase in the

Fig. 9. Emission spectra of CdS in 0.058 mol dm⁻³ AOT in heptane at various *W* values.

size of the colloids which brings about a decrease in the energy of those traps. The relative fluorescence quantum yield decreases and the fluorescence half-width increases as *W* increases (Table 2). The red-shifting of the emission peak with increase of CdS concentration in a given water pool *W* = 5 (Table 6) again confirms the formation of larger clusters with higher concentration. Injection of electron scavengers like MV²⁺ and Pt and hole scavengers like HCOO⁻ and C₂O₄²⁻ into the inner water pools of the reverse micelles effectively quench the semiconductor emission by capturing electrons/holes from the conduction/valence band of the

Fig. 10. Emission spectra of CdS in 0.058 mol dm⁻³ AOT in heptane at various concentration of CdS prepared in *W* = 5 reverse micelles.

Fig. 11. Emission spectra of CdS without quencher (a) and with quenchers : (b) C₂O₄²⁻, (c) HCOO⁻, (d) MV²⁺ and (e) Pt.

nanoparticles. This can be verified from the results presented in Table 7. In similar experiment Henglein¹⁸ studied the fluorescence of colloidal CdS in aqueous medium and observed similar quenching of luminescence in presence of MV²⁺ and TI⁺.

Mixed semiconductor particles :

We have prepared nano-sized semiconductor particles Zn_xCd_{1-x}S and studied the quantum-size effect. The size of the water pool as well as the components constituting the reverse micelle have effect on the semiconductor properties. The band gap energies of the nanosized mixed semiconductors in the two media are presented as functions of *x* and *W* in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. Δ*E*_g denotes the band

Table 2. Band gap energies of Zn_xCd_{1-x}S as a function of *x* and *W* in AOT-heptane-water

[Zn_xCd_{1-x}S] = 7 × 10⁻⁴ M, ([Zn²⁺] + [Cd²⁺])/[S²⁻] = 1, [AOT] = 0.058 M

<i>x</i>	0	0.14	0.25	0.50	0.75	0.86	1
<i>W</i> = 5							
<i>E</i> (<i>R</i>)(eV)	2.73	2.76	2.81	2.89	3.03	3.18	4.00
ΔE_g^a (eV)	0.33	0.18	0.09	-0.14	-0.32	-0.30	0.34
$\Delta E^*{}^b$ (eV)	-	-0.15	-0.24	-0.48	-0.65	-0.64	-
<i>W</i> = 8							
<i>E</i> (<i>R</i>)(eV)	2.70	2.72	2.76	2.79	2.85	3.70	3.94
ΔE_g^a (eV)	0.30	0.14	0.04	-0.24	-0.50	0.22	0.28
ΔE^* (eV)	-	-0.16	-0.28	-0.53	-0.78	-0.06	-
<i>W</i> = 14							
<i>E</i> (<i>R</i>)(eV)	2.67	2.70	2.71	2.73	3.55	3.65	3.88
ΔE_g^a (eV)	0.27	0.12	0.01	-0.30	-0.20	0.12	0.22
ΔE^* (eV)	-	-0.14	-0.26	-0.55	-0.03	-0.06	-
<i>W</i> = 20							
<i>E</i> (<i>R</i>)(eV)	2.60	2.64	2.69	3.18	3.48	3.65	3.82
ΔE_g^a (eV)	0.20	0.06	-0.03	0.15	0.13	0.17	0.16
ΔE^* (eV)	-	-0.13	-0.22	-0.03	-0.04	-0.00	-

^a $\Delta E_g = E(R) - E_g$, *E*(*R*) denotes the observed band gap energy in the pool and *E_g* represents the bulk band gap energy of a homogeneous solid solution having the same composition as that in the pool. The bulk band gap energies of ZnS and CdS are 3.66 and 2.4 eV, respectively.

^b $\Delta E^* = E(R) - E^*(R)$ and *E*^{*}(*R*) symbolizes the ideal band gap energy for a homogeneous solid solution in pool and as such ΔE^* may be considered as a measure of deviation from ideality (inhomogeneity).

Table 3. Band gap energies of Zn_xCd_{1-x}S as a function of *x* and *W* in CTAB-chloroform-water

[Zn_xCd_{1-x}S] = 7 × 10⁻⁴ M, ([Zn²⁺] + [Cd²⁺])/[S²⁻] = 1, [CTAB] = 0.232 M

<i>x</i>	0	0.14	0.25	0.50	0.75	0.86	1
<i>W</i> = 0.50							
<i>E</i> (<i>R</i>)(eV)	2.70	2.89	3.06	3.40	3.65	3.74	3.94
ΔE_g^a (eV)	0.30	0.31	0.34	0.37	0.30	0.26	0.28
ΔE^* (eV)	-	0.01	0.05	0.08	0.02	-0.02	-
<i>W</i> = 1.25							
<i>E</i> (<i>R</i>)(eV)	2.67	2.87	3.05	3.33	3.60	3.70	3.88
ΔE_g^a (eV)	0.27	0.29	0.33	0.30	0.25	0.22	0.22
ΔE^* (eV)	-	0.03	0.08	0.05	0.02	0.00	-
<i>W</i> = 2.00							
<i>E</i> (<i>R</i>)(eV)	2.64	2.82	2.95	3.27	3.55	3.67	3.82
ΔE_g^a (eV)	0.24	0.24	0.23	0.24	0.20	0.19	0.16
ΔE^* (eV)	-	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.02	-0.02	-
<i>W</i> = 3.50							
<i>E</i> (<i>R</i>)(eV)	2.61	2.74	2.92	3.18	3.50	3.65	3.82
ΔE_g^a (eV)	0.21	0.16	0.20	0.15	0.15	0.17	0.16
ΔE^* (eV)	-	-0.04	0.01	-0.03	-0.02	0.00	-
<i>W</i> = 5.00							
<i>E</i> (<i>R</i>)(eV)	2.56	2.70	2.89	3.14	3.43	3.55	3.76
ΔE_g^a (eV)	0.16	0.12	0.17	0.11	0.08	0.07	0.10
ΔE^* (eV)	-	-0.03	0.03	-0.02	-0.03	-0.04	-

gap shift. The band gap energy of homogeneous solid solutions of two semiconductors lies between those of the contributing species and is for an ideal solution given by

$$E = xE_1 + (1-x) E_2 \quad (2)$$

where *x* is the mole fraction of the component with band gap energy *E*₁ and *E*₂ is the band gap energy of the other component. Fig. 12 indicates that *E*(*R*) of Zn_xCd_{1-x}S, stabilised in CTAB-chloroform-water system, is a linear function of *x* as predicted by eq. (2). Fig. 13 reveals that the *E*(*R*) vs *x* curve of Zn_xCd_{1-x}S stabilised in AOT-heptane-water exhibits negative deviation from ideality, indicating an inhomogeneous nature of the nanocrystals of the mixed semiconductor. The departure from ideal behaviour may be attributed to the binding of Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ ions to different extents on the negatively charged interface of AOT-water within the pool as the binding constants of the two ions are not same²⁰.

Fig. 12. Dependence of band gap energy of Zn_xCd_{1-x}S, stabilised in CTAB-chloroform-water (*W* = 3.5), on concentration of Zn (molar percent).

Particle radii depends linearly with water content *W*. This is evident from Fig. 14. For the particles incorporated in AOT-heptane-water the dependence may be expressed by the equations :

$$R_{CdS}(A) = 0.21 W + 21.8 \quad (3a)$$

Fig. 13. Dependence of band gap energy of $Zn_xCd_{1-x}S$, stabilized in AOT-heptane-water ($W = 5$), on concentration of Zn (molar percent).

Fig. 14. Variation in particle radius R_{CdS} with water content W in (a) CTAB-chloroform-water, (b) AOT-heptane water.

$$R_{ZnS} \text{ (Å)} = 0.47 W + 20.4 \quad (3b)$$

while the same relations for CTAB-chloroform-water may be represented as

$$R_{CdS} \text{ (Å)} = 1.36 W + 22.9 \quad (4a)$$

$$R_{ZnS} \text{ (Å)} = 2.55 W + 25.2 \quad (4b)$$

In a given pool R_{ZnS} and R_{CdS} have been determined using the Brus equation with experimentally determined values of

Table 5. Fluorescence of CdS in reverse micelles
 $[AOT] = 0.058 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $x = 1$, $\lambda_{ex} = 380 \text{ nm}$, $[CdS] = 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

W	λ_{max} nm	r^* ϕ_F	$10^{-2} \nu$
4	554	1	505
6	563	0.90	538
8	584	0.81	599
10	595	0.59	694
12	636	0.35	735

ϕ_F^* stands for the relative fluorescence quantum yield and ν stands for the fluorescence half-width.

Table 6. Fluorescence of CdS in reverse micelles
 $[AOT] = 0.058 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $x = 1$, $\lambda_{ex} = 380 \text{ nm}$, $W = 5$

$10^{-4} [CdS]$ mol dm ⁻³	λ_{max} nm	ϕ_F^*	$10^{-2} \nu$
2	553	0.48	699
4	560	0.74	667
6	567	0.56	694
8	574	1	641

Table 7. Quenching of CdS mission by electron and hole scavengers
 $[AOT] = 0.058 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $x = 1$, $\lambda_{ex} = 380 \text{ nm}$, $[CdS] = 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $W = 5$

Scavenger	[Scavenger] mol dm ⁻³	λ_{max} nm	ϕ_F^*	$10^{-2} \nu$ cm ⁻¹
-	-	562	1	855
COONa	2×10^{-4}	563	0.92	885
COONa	-	-	-	-
HCOONa	2×10^{-4}	563	0.83	909
MV ²⁺	1×10^{-6}	565	0.66	909
Pt* (1.5 wt%)	-	574	0.09	833

*Deposited photochemically on CdS surface by the reported method.

ΔE_g and the reported values of ϵ , m_e and m_h for CdS and ZnS^{21,22}. The radius R_M of $Zn_xCd_{1-x}S$ incorporated in CTAB-chloroform water has been evaluated from the following linear relation :

Table 4. $R_M \Delta E_g$ as a function of $1/R_M$ of mixed crystalline solid solutions of $Zn_xCd_{1-x}S$ in CTAB-chloroform-water system

W	W = 0.50		W = 1.25		W = 2.00		W = 3.50		W = 5.00		eM
	$R_M \Delta E_g$	$1/R_M^*$									
	eV Å	Å ⁻¹									
0.14	7.409	0.0418	7.290	0.0398	6.382	0.0376	4.434	0.0361	3.704	0.0324	2.39
0.25	8.203	0.0414	8.432	0.0391	6.279	0.0366	5.655	0.0354	5.410	0.0314	4.71
0.50	9.121	0.0406	7.950	0.0377	6.948	0.0345	4.440	0.0338	3.746	0.0294	2.27
0.75	7.553	0.0392	6.863	0.0364	6.120	0.0327	4.639	0.0323	2.902	0.0276	3.46
0.86	6.604	0.0394	6.129	0.0359	5.949	0.0319	5.353	0.0318	2.606	0.0269	5.79

* $\epsilon = 5.7$ and 5.13 , $m_e = 0.17 m_0$ and $0.205 m_0$ and $m_h = 0.7 m_0$ and $0.51 m_0$ for CdS and ZnS, respectively.

$$R_M = x R_{ZnS} + (1-x)R_{CdS} \quad (5)$$

The dielectric constants ϵ_M of the mixed semiconductor nanoparticles have been determined from the intercepts of the straight-lines obtained by plotting $R_M \Delta E_g$ against $1/R_M$. The intercepts of the mean straight-lines have been computed by the method of least-squares. The values of the ϵ_M , as a function of x , have been compiled in Table 4.

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